

Personalised Artificial Intelligence Chatbot using Machine learning Techniques

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Abstract — Using text or speech approaches, computer software with artificial intelligence (AI) known as a Chatbot may simulate a conversation. Chatbots are built on artificial intelligence, which evaluates client data and mixes it with the response. Since AI-powered bots are significantly more powerful and can complete multiple tasks at once, they can take over a range of responsibilities. A bot can communicate in the most natural way possible, thanks to natural language processing. The ideal user-Chabot link combines modern technology with human intervention.

The core intelligence of ALICE is built on the Artificial Intelligence Markup Language (AIML), which enables programmers to describe the fundamentals of chatbot knowledge. ALICE uses a straightforward pattern-matching algorithm. Like Smarter Child in 2001, chatbots were created and made accessible through message programmes. Virtual personal assistants like Apple Siri, Microsoft Cortana, Amazon Alexa, Google Assistant, and IBM Watson were developed as the next step.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advancement and evaluation of intelligent hardware and software, also known as intelligent agents, artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly integrating into our regular lifestyle. Intelligent agents are able to accomplish a wide variety of tasks, from simple human labour to complicated things. One of the most basic and widespread aspects of smart Human-Computer Interaction, a chatbot is a typical example of an AI system (HCI). It is a computer programme that responds smartly to text or voice interactions and uses natural language processing to grasp one or more human languages (NLP). Smart bots, interactive agents, digital assistants, and artificial conversation entities are other identities for chatbots.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Turing Test, which asks "Can machines think?," was put forth by Alan Turing in 1950, and it was at this time that the concept of a chatbot gained popularity. Eliza, a chatbot created in 1966 with the intention of serving as a user's virtual psychotherapist, returned user utterances in the form of questions. It made use of a template-based response mechanism and straightforward pattern matching. Although it had poor conversational skills, it was nonetheless able to perplex users at a time when they were not accustomed to talking with computers, which inspired them to begin creating more chatbots. A chatbot dubbed PARRY that was created in 1972 was an upgrade over ELIZA. The chatbot ALICE was created in 1995 and won the Loebner Prize, also known as the annual Turing Test, in 2000, 2001, and 2004. The title of "most human computer" was initially attained by this machine.

III. CHATBOT PROGRESS

A. A critique of the chat interface This component represents the ui. Its purpose is to gather user requests from end consumers, which the system uses as intake. It is also accountable for displaying to the user the system's output. As a result, it can be stated that the chat interface optimizes all communication and functions as the system's public face. It serves as a link between the system and the user. The request that the user initiates through the chat interface is conveyed to the chat backend, which operates as a message pipeline between the chat interface and the machine learning layer. To access the interface, you can either use a webpage or a smartphone app. The type of ui to be chosen is governed by the customer requirement that the system must satisfy. When accessed from a smartphone or computer, the system's ui will look like an application, and when viewed from a Desktop computer, it will look like a webpage. Swift will be required to develop mobile apps for iOS or Android. In this scenario, only the Android ui platform will be developed; all backend processing will actually occur on the server where the system will be

deployed.

Fig 1: Development of Chabot

➤ Smart chat bots made up of NLU, NLG and ML engines have the following components:

Fig 2: Architecture Of Chabot

B. An assessment of NLU Engine Natural Language Understanding, also known as NLU, is a subsidiary of NLP (Natural Language Processing) that makes it possible a system to grasp natural language or a conversation. The users' native tongue. Conversational language used by users in day-to-day interactions is not as organised as the formal language is perfect. It does not place a lot of emphasis on the vocabulary and grammar. It then becomes It's demanding for a system to fully understand what the sentence implies. The user's input was received in unstructured text that the system cannot directly recognise. It only considers input in formats with structure. A component of NLP (Natural Language Processing), Natural Language Understanding (also known as NLU) allows a system to grasp natural language or a chat. Language spoken by the users. The common speech that people use in chat is not as organized as the formal language. The vocab and grammar are not given a lot of emphasis. It then transforms into A system needs to work hard to comprehend all that the text conveys. The system was unable to directly acknowledge the user's input because it was received as unstructured information. It merely takes into consideration input in structured formats.

C. An analysis of word segmentation The procedure of dividing text into concise and meaningful parts is also known as tokenization. Sentences, clauses, phrases, words,

paragraphs, and sometimes even alphabets can be taken into account as these components. The letters are the smallest unit. The division of sentences into words and spaces is known as word segmentation. Sentence tokens are the tokenized portions of the sentences. The tokenizers separated the phrases into discrete chunks of words and punctuation. The most popular tokenizer, or space type tokenizer, breaks down phrases into words at empty spaces. The tokenizer must also take into consideration abbreviations, acronyms, dates, decimal numbers, and other words that cannot be separated at punctuation and blank spaces without losing their meaning.

D. An analysis of POS Tagging POS Tagging is the technique of giving specific words in phrases grammatical annotations. The Parts-Of-Speech Tags are included in these annotations. Based on the word's dependence on other words in that phrase, clause, sentence, paragraph, etc., they indicate the sentence's grammatical importance. Noun, verb, pronoun, and other POS tags are frequently used. The POS Tagging process can be carried out in a variety of ways.

E. Examining Dependency Parsing A dependency parser is used to establish the connection between the words in a sentence based on the grammatical tags associated with the phrase. It comes after parsing as the next step. For each statement, a dependency tree or graph is produced. The dependency tree and parsing tree are other names for this tree. The parser can be incorporated using a variety of approaches.

F. An examination of synonyms and pattern recognition No statement provided by the user can precisely match any sentence in the database, regardless of how huge our data collection is. But not every statement means the same thing. The database is then searched for a sentence with the same purpose after understanding the user sentence's aim. The matching sentences use several words to convey the same concepts in various ways.

G. An analysis of the decision or ML engine Chatbots that are repetitive or scripted have predetermined responses to deliver. They respond to the user's question by selecting a response from a collection of predefined responses that have been categorised. By incorporating ML, chatbots may compute the responses from scratch. It is used to forecast the answers to customer inquiries and to update the system based on past performance. As fresh information from the user is encountered, it continuously updates the databases. This engine analyses what the user requests using supervised, unsupervised, or both methodologies. Additionally, it makes use of a model to decipher the user's intent and deliver the proper outcomes. Predictions or any other type of analysis based on the use and evaluation of logical representations may be the results. The majority of machine learning models use statistical and probabilistic analyses of the actual occurrences as the foundation for their predictions for the test instance.

H. NLG Engine evaluation In contrast to NLU, NLG completes the task. It involves converting a system's output

into user-understandable plain language representations. In other words, NLG is the process of producing text or voice using patterns that are generated by the system. The system's results are presented in a structured fashion for the system's convenience in understanding and processing them. NLG delivers the System knowledge base in a way that the user may easily understand—natural or conversational language. The same sentence can be said in a variety of different ways. The sentences may be written in either the active voice or the passive voice. Furthermore, although they could use synonyms, two phrases can sound similar to one another. Therefore, the NLG unit must analyse all possible ways to understand the same language before choosing the best one when giving a response to the user.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Context recognition: Pre-processing is done on the input sentence to filter it so that it passes system specifications. The proper setting is selected depending on the message's characteristics.

Response system with AIML: The user is trying to interact normally with the bot, and the input is mapped to the proper pattern in the AIML files. If an answer is available, the user gets it.

Question Analysis and Response System: when asked personal questions like "hi, hello," "what are you doing?" To extract keywords, the input text is examined. Using the keywords, the dataset is searched for the information the user requested.

1. This module will offer the user with the information they require when they request it. The user will be provided with the proper response if their input matches a pattern in the AIML files. Keywords are pulled from the input if the AIML files don't have anything for that query pattern.

2. Consider the scenario where we return the response if the sentence is located with a confidence level > 0.5. And the bot will generate, give some information, etc., if it does not understand what the user is giving it.

3. The activity can be stopped by the user by saying goodbye if they are happy with the bot's response and do not want to chat any further.

Benefits

- Instantaneous responses to all common queries
- 24 hour service
- Intelligent conversational personalization
- Implementation of messaging, mobile, and web apps
- Eliminate tedious time-consuming tasks

V. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The following components should make up a typical chatbot architecture:

- ❖ A chat session, window, or application front end interface.
- ❖ NLP's deep learning model for processing natural language.
- ❖ A corpus or training dataset for the application database used to train the NLP model and process chatbot action data.

Fig 3: System Architecture

A) Training or Corpus Data: An NLP model can be trained to comprehend human speech or text and to respond in a way that is similar to it using corpora, which are collections of data. Many human interactions are frequently found in large-scale corpora.

B) Chatbot window: We have created a feature that allows users to communicate with bots via text. In the absence of a break or quit request, the function keeps the chat window open.

C) Examine or try out the chatbot: There may be several ways to communicate with and assess the developed text bot.

D) Data pre-processing : Transform all data provided by the user or the corpus to either uppercase letters or lowercase letters. This will stop words from being misspelt or misunderstood, regardless of whether they are written in lowercase or uppercase.

E) Tokenization: Make a sentence (or any group of words) into a single word.

Fig 4: Tokenization process

F) Stemming: Finding similarities between words with the same root words requires some work. By connecting

related words to their corresponding root words, this will enable us to reduce the number of words on the list.

G) Generate BOW [Bag of Words]: Words are transformed into numbers by creating vector embeddings from the above-mentioned tokens. The neural network model uses this as an input to understand the textual content.

Fig 5: Bag of words

VI. MODULES

- **Intents.json:** Intents classification, often known as recognition, is the process of taking a spoken word or written text and classifying it according to the user's goals.
- **Training.py:** the domain, configuration, endpoint, intent, actions, slots, tales, and general file structure of the chatbot are all described in this section. The code will train an NLU and conversation model to obtain the Responses. The model folder houses the trained models. It will start the server with actions in addition to running the chatbot on the command line. Run this code only because doing otherwise will start run.py and actions. Training.py, which is invoked by the chatbot module, contains the modules required to run it via the command line

VII. IMPLEMENTATION

- ❖ A chatbot can be implemented using a variety of methods. Developers can choose the algorithms, platforms, and tools to design the chatbot with the help of an understanding of what it will offer and what category it belongs to. Additionally, it aids end users in anticipating what will happen.
- ❖ Accurate knowledge representation, an answer generation approach, and a library of ready-made neutral responses to employ when a user's statement cannot be interpreted are all criteria for developing a chatbot. Any system must be initially broken down into its component elements in accordance with a standard to allow for a modular development method to be used.

- ❖ The process begins when a user asks a question, like "need Help!?" Use a messaging service, such as Facebook, Slack, WhatsApp, WeChat, or Skype, or a text- or voice-based app, such as Amazon Echo, to communicate with the chatbot.
- ❖ The Language Understanding Component parses the user request once the chatbot gets it to determine the user's goal and the information related to it (intent: "translate," entities: [word: "help"]).
- ❖ A chatbot must decide what to do next after arriving at the best interpretation it can. It can immediately take action based on the new information, recall what it has learned and wait to see what occurs next, seek for more context, or ask for clarification.
- ❖ As soon as the request is understood, operations are made and data is retrieved. The chatbot performs the requested actions or gets the requested information from its data sources, which can be either an external resource that can be accessed through an API call or a database that the chatbot refers to as its Knowledge Base.
- ❖ In order to give the user a natural language answer that The Response Generation Component uses Natural Language Generation to produce speech that closely resembles human speech after retrieval (NLG). This response was given in response to the context and intent details the User Message Analysis Component had supplied. One of the three models—the retrieval model, the rule-based model, or the generating model—generates the required responses.
- ❖ The context of a conversation, which consists of the present intent, identified entities, or missing entities necessary to satisfy user requests, is maintained and updated by a dialogue management component. Additionally, it asks follow-up questions, analyses user clarifications, and seeks missing data.

```

Start messaging with the bot (type quit to stop)!
User: hi
1/1 [=====] - 0s 263ms/step
ChatBot: Hello
User: who are you
1/1 [=====] - 0s 15ms/step
ChatBot: I.m Netbusbot, your bot assistant
User: quit
    
```

Fig 6: Chatting process

VIII. RESULT

A chatbot system's goal is to mimic a human conversation. Its architecture combines a language model with a computational method to simulate information online exchange using natural language between a human and a computer.

```
... Start messaging with the bot (type quit to stop)!
User: hey
1/1 [=====] - 0s 62ms/step
ChatBot: Hi there
User: Who are you
1/1 [=====] - 0s 27ms/step
ChatBot: I'm Netbusbot, an Artificial Intelligent bot
User: what should I call you
1/1 [=====] - 0s 18ms/step
ChatBot: I'm Netbusbot!
User: Could you help me?
1/1 [=====] - 0s 19ms/step
ChatBot: Tell me how can assist you with the Netbus E-ticketing Services
User: how to cancel a ticket
1/1 [=====] - 0s 20ms/step
ChatBot: Just go to our web site and follow the guidelines to cancel the ticket
User: thank you
1/1 [=====] - 0s 19ms/step
ChatBot: My pleasure
User: good bie
1/1 [=====] - 0s 23ms/step
ChatBot: Bye! Come back again
```

```
Start messaging with the bot (type quit to stop)!
User: hello
1/1 [=====] - 0s 225ms/step
ChatBot: Hello
User: give me a hand please
1/1 [=====] - 0s 20ms/step
ChatBot: Yes Sure, How can I support you
User: I want to raise a complaint
1/1 [=====] - 0s 19ms/step
ChatBot: Please mention your complaint, we will reach you and sorry for any inconvenience caused
User: ok
1/1 [=====] - 0s 22ms/step
ChatBot: Have a nice day
User: thank you
1/1 [=====] - 0s 24ms/step
ChatBot: My pleasure
User: bi
1/1 [=====] - 0s 19ms/step
ChatBot: See you later
User: quit
```

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IX. CONCLUSION

In my opinion, artificial intelligence-powered chatbots and smart assistants are transforming society. Creating a simple chatbot is convenient than one that is more difficult and complicated, but creators must be conscious of and take into account issues like reliability, expandability, and flexibility as well as a greater standard of purpose in natural speech.. When using messaging apps to reach a large audience, chatbots outperform humans. In the near future, they might serve as an efficient method for acquiring information.

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